

CEOS Data Management and Stewardship Maturity Matrix in support to Earth Observation data preservation and curation

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Science and Earth Observation data represent today a unique and valuable asset for humankind that should be preserved without time constraints and kept accessible and exploitable by current and future generations. In Earth Science, knowledge of the past and tracking of the future evolution are at the basis of our capability to effectively respond to the global changes that are putting increasing pressure on the environment, and on human society. This task becomes increasingly challenging in view of the existing 50 years' worth of Earth Science data stored in archives around the world and the massive increase of data volumes from latest generation missions like e.g. the European Copernicus Sentinels. Preservation of these data and curation throughout their lifecycle is crucial to ensure that they will continue to be accessible, with all supporting information needed to ensure authenticity and understandability, in the long term future. Data Curation activities focus on data and information consolidation and archiving, discovery and access, quality maintenance and improvement, value adding and re-use over time.

The CEOS WGISS (Committee on Earth Observation Satellites, Working Group on Information Systems and Services) working group has drafted in the recent years a series of best practices and guidelines addressing different aspects of data preservation and curation. In particular, the CEOS WGISS Data Management and Stewardship Maturity Matrix (DMSMM) [1], which represents the result of a combined analysis performed in consultation with the European Data Access and Preservation Working Group (DAP WG), and its application is described in detail in this paper.

The DMSMM Matrix is a fundamental instrument supporting data curators in the: 1) definition of maturity targets to be achieved for Earth observation datasets to satisfy at best designated user community needs, 2) definition of preservation and curation activities and improvement roadmaps needed to reach the defined target, 3) measurement of achievements. The matrix addresses all aspects of the data lifecycle including preservation, data and information content consolidation and improvement, quality, accessibility, and usability of data and metadata. It can also be used to create stewardship maturity scoreboard of dataset(s) and to provide overall data maturity (e.g. quality and usability) information to users, stakeholders, and decision makers.

Keywords: Best Practice; Provenance; Data Preservation; Processes; Lifecycle; Data Valorisation

Introduction

This document presents the WGISS Data Management and Stewardship maturity assessment model in the form of a matrix for Earth Observation datasets. The WGISS Data Management and Stewardship Maturity Matrix (DMSMM) [1] represents the result of a combined analysis on the “Long-Term Scientific Data Stewardship” Maturity Matrix [3] and DMP-IG [2] performed in consultation by the Data Access and Preservation Working Group at European level and by the WGISS Data Stewardship Interest Group (<https://ceos.org/ourwork/workinggroups/wgiss/preservation/>). The resulting Matrix includes also the Research for Data Alliance (RDA) FAIR principles results [4] and the Earthnet Data Assessment Pilot (EDAP) Quality input [5] produced as part of WGISS cooperation with the CEOS Working Group on Data Calibration and Validation (WGCV- <https://ceos.org/ourwork/workinggroups/wgcv/>).

Figure-1: WGISS DMSMM definition process

Intended Audience

This document is intended to assist data managers in Earth Observation (EO) data centres in the task of ensuring Earth Observation space data sets long-term preservation, curation, accessibility, discoverability and usability.

The intended audience comprises:

1. Data providers: to evaluate and improve the quality and usability of their products;
2. Modellers, decision-makers, and scientists: to improve their products, to make investments and take decisions;
3. Data managers/stewards of data centres and repositories: to validate their compliance or lack of stewardship practice or standards, to assess the current state of their data holdings and repositories, to create a roadmap to improve or enhance the stewardship maturity of practices applied to all data holdings.

The Data Curator is the role identified for DMSMM compilation. Data curation involves annotation, publication and presentation of the data such that the value of the data is maintained over time, and the data remains available for reuse and preservation. Data curation includes "all the processes needed for a controlled data creation, maintenance, and management, together with the capacity to add value to data".

Earth Observation Domain Applicability

The WGISS Data Management and Stewardship Maturity Matrix may be adopted to facilitate and improve CEOS Agencies Data Management and Stewardship activities and achievements. It can be further tailored to take into account specific Earth Observation requirements and already existing Best Practices available internationally or at Agency level. A dataset appraisal activity should initially define the desired level to be reached for each maturity matrix component, for a specific mission/dataset, for example based on:

- Mapping versus final user exploitation capabilities;
- Mapping w.r.t. data preservation commitments, budgets, responsibilities and preservation requirements.

Different missions' datasets can have different targets and varying maturity level ratings.

WGISS Data Management and Stewardship Maturity Matrix

The collaborative WGISS DMSMM fully addresses and covers data preservation, discoverability, accessibility, quality and usability aspects including data use related services and capabilities. The WGISS Data Management and Stewardship Maturity Matrix is aligned with the following definitions:

- Data stewardship "encompasses all activities that preserve and improve the information content, accessibility, and usability of data and metadata" (National Research Council 2007);
- Data management "includes all activities for planning, execution and oversight of policies, practices and projects that acquire, control, protect, deliver and enhance the value of data and information assets." (Mosely et al. 2009).

The main objective of its application and use is to measure and verify the overall implemented (or to be implemented) data preservation and stewardship lifecycle. The Matrix can be used as a self-assessment tool to create a stewardship maturity scoreboard target for one or more scientific dataset(s), identify actual and potential gaps, and define a roadmap for data stewardship improvement; or to provide data quality and usability information to users, stakeholders, and decision makers.

It is flexible and adaptable through a tailoring, with respect to the requirements and objectives of the data owners, highlighted after the initial process foreseen in the CEOS WGISS Data Preservation Workflow [1]. The WGISS DMSMM will allow data owners to:

- apply a reference model for stewardship planning and resources allocation;
- define goals and targets and create a roadmap for scientific data stewardship improvement;
- apply detailed guidelines and recommendations for data preservation and stewardship and self-evaluate the levels and results achieved;

- help to break down problems related to preservation and stewardship, and to understand the costs associated with each level;
- provide data quality and usability information to end users, stakeholders, and decision makers;
- give a technical evaluation of the level of preservation while helping with self-assessment of preservation;
- define goal levels for the funding agencies.

	DISCOVERABILITY				USABILITY				PRESERVATION				CURATION	
	IMMFP Metadata for Discovery	IMMFP Online Access	IMMFP Data Encoding	MAMA Data Documentation	IMMFP Data Traceability	IMMFP Data Validation	IMMFP Data Uncertainty	IMMFP Data Quality Control	IMMFP Data Preservation	IMMFP Data Verification	IMMFP Data Reprocessing/Reprocessing	IMMFP2 Persistence & Reusable Metadata		
Level 0 - Not Managed	1) No catalogue available 2) No advertising available	Data and metadata are not accessible online	1) Data Not Structured 2) Non-standard or proprietary data formats or poorly documented standard file formats.	Partial and incomplete mission documentation	1) Limited product information available (not online)	1) Reference Data Representativeness: No validation 2) Reference Data Quality: No validation 3) Validation Method: No validation 4) Validation Results: No validation	1) Uncertainty Method: Uncertainty characterization not performed, or method not documented. 2) Uncertainty Sources: Uncertainty characterization not performed, or sources analysed not documented. 3) Uncertainty Values: No uncertainty information provided.	1) No control and monitoring check 2) No quality indicator metadata 3) No procedures documented	1) Uncontrolled storage location 2) Data are not stored 3) Data Records archiving managed 4) Relevant information on Product Details Assessment not made available	No Data/Associated Information Integrity, Authority and Readability check	1) No reprocessing activities planned 2) Pre-flight calibration & characterisation not documented or information not available. 3) Post-launch calibration & characterisation not documented or not available. 4) Processing: Additional processing steps not documented.	No persistent and reusable identifiers available		
Level 1 - Partially Managed	1) Advertising available 2) Catalogue search available at product level with minimum set of metadata	Basic online services available for data and metadata access	1) Basic schema for automated data use available in documented standard file format. 2) Periodically updating conventions used.	1) Already existent mission documentation available and preserved for the long term. 2) No link between mission documentation and data records	1) Product information available (not online)	1) Reference Data Representativeness: measurements created to be mostly representative of the satellite measurements, covering a primary range latitude of measurements and an ad-hoc opportunities. 2) Reference Data Quality: single uncertainty for the entire dataset. 3) Validation Method: single uncertainty estimated 4) Validation Results: Validation results show good agreement between satellite and reference measurements within uncertainties in most cases.	1) Uncertainty Method: Limited use of GUM approach, and/or, an expanded comparison measurements to other sensors. 2) Uncertainty Sources: Most important sources of uncertainty included. 3) Uncertainty Values: Single uncertainty value provided for subsets of data	1) Basic data quality control and monitoring check 2) Minimal set of quality control procedures documented and available	1) Basic archiving for original data records preservation 2) Assessment of SW preservation 3) Product Details 4) Additional processing steps documented. Any required information missing.	Data Records/Associated Information Integrity basic check	1) Minor updates and bugs corrections of data records implemented 2) Data Records re-packing and/or re-formatting 3) Pre-flight calibration & characterisation misses some important aspects of instrument behaviour and/or is not entirely of a level of quality to be judged fit for purpose 4) Post-launch calibration & characterisation misses some important aspects of instrument behaviour and/or is not entirely of a level of quality to be judged fit for purpose. 5) Additional processing steps documented. Some important additional processing steps may not be fit for stated purpose.	1) Persistent identifier assignment only for particular Data Records Collections 2) Basic landing page management		
Level 2 - Managed	1) Detailed catalogue search available at product level 2) Product metadata oriented towards an international standard 3) Data Records Collection and Associated Information searchible. 4) Collection metadata oriented towards an international standard	1) Simple Access Architecture through metadata 2) Data access system oriented towards an international standard	1) Use of non-proprietary international standards provided for specific interoperability. 2) Periodically re-packing/re-formatting of archive data. 3) Data in well documented standard file format, community using common standards.	1) Documentation provided, published and well described 2) Link between mission documentation and data records created and managed	1) Dataset tested for presence of correct provenance metadata. Well described product information available online	1) Reference Data Representativeness: measurements created to be well representative of the satellite measurements and covering a reasonable range of the satellite's full range of measurements and with full agreement of uncertainties and carried out on a regular basis determined by product performance. 2) Reference Data Quality: Full uncertainty information, assessed following the GUM and traceable to community reference data w.r.t. their uncertainties 3) Validation Method: assess satellite measurements and reference data w.r.t. their uncertainties 4) Validation Results show excellent agreement between satellite and reference measurements, within uncertainties. Analysis performed independently of satellite mission owner.	1) Uncertainty Method: GUM approach to estimate measurement uncertainty with full breakdown of components and separated type or classification. 2) Uncertainty Sources: All important sources of uncertainty included. 3) Uncertainty Values: Total uncertainty per pixel is provided, with basic breakdown of key components to error covariance.	1) Quality indicator post processing available 2) Quality control procedures documented and available online	1) Preservation repository certified internally 2) Product Details Assessment: All required information available, any recommended information missing	1) Data Records/Associated Information context integrity check and verification 2) Media readability and accessibility testing	1) Reprocessing for calibration and/or algorithm improvement 2) Pre-flight calibration & characterisation covers all responsible aspects of instrument behaviour to a quality that is "fit for purpose" in terms of the mission's stated performance. Calibration traceable to SI or community reference, characterisation meets good practice. 3) Post-launch calibration & characterisation covers all responsible aspects of instrument behaviour to a quality that is "fit for purpose" in terms of the mission's stated performance and uses appropriate community infrastructure/methods (CCSDS/IRMS). 4) Processing: Additional processing steps documented. All additional processing steps fit for stated purpose.	1) Persistent identifier assignment to all disseminated Data Records Collections and metadata 2) Automatic landing page generation and intensive management of landing pages		
Level 3 - Fully Managed	1) Product rich metadata fully compliant with an international standard 2) Collection metadata fully compliant with an international standard 3) Catalogue accessible via an accepted international or community agreed open standards protocol 4) Data policy on the use conditions/restrictions and legal constraints of the data, available in metadata 5) Periodic updates of metadata in the catalogue 6) Quality indicator metadata available and discoverable 7) Search results ordered by relevancy 8) Seamless transition from discovery to access	1) Data and metadata access system fully compliant with an international standard 2) Data policy regarding user conditions and restrictions of the data or community agreed open standards protocol 3) Visualization services allowing a user to view images of data 4) Reporting system 5) Hosted processing 6) Data updates to standards evolution 7) Data and metadata accessible through a free access protocol	1) Accepted and Available semantic encoding standards for complete interoperability 2) Data and metadata available in well documented standard file format, community using common standards. 3) Automatic metadata generation for provenance documentation 4) Complete and updated data processing available online	1) Standards based metadata for provenance documentation and data records published	1) Automatic metadata generation for provenance documentation 2) Complete and updated data processing available online	1) Reference Data Representativeness: Reference measurements independently assessed to be fully representative of the satellite measurements, covering the satellite's full range of measurements and with full agreement of uncertainties and carried out on a regular basis determined by product performance. 2) Reference Data Quality: Full uncertainty and error-correlation information, assessed following the GUM and traceable to SI 3) Validation Method: assess satellite measurements and reference data w.r.t. their error-covariance and validates those uncertainties. 4) Validation Results show excellent agreement between satellite and reference measurements, within uncertainties. Uncertainty validated. Analysis performed independently of satellite mission owner.	1) Uncertainty Method: GUM approach to estimate measurement uncertainty, including a treatment of error-covariance. 2) Uncertainty Sources: All reasonable sources of uncertainty included. 3) Uncertainty Values: Uncertainties per pixel provided with error-covariance information for all appropriate components.	1) Data quality control fully compliant with an international standard 2) Quality indicator pre and post processing available in the metadata 3) Quality metadata assessed	1) Preservation repository certified internally 2) Periodic technology refreshment 3) Identify and manage the basic preservation of relevant mission SW, ensuring that preserved data can be processed 4) Continuity of service availability 5) Product Details Assessment: All required and recommended information available	1) Automatic Data Records/Associated Information context integrity check and verification 2) Data authenticity verifiable internally and by the final user 3) Automatic verification process, including monitoring and reporting	1) Reprocessing for time-series creation 2) Readings for technology evolution 3) Metadata includes information about the licence under which the data is to be reused 4) Pre-flight: At Level-2, additional calibration and characterisation includes the measurements needed to assess uncertainties at component level and their impact on the final product. 5) Post-launch calibration & characterisation covers all responsible aspects of instrument behaviour to a quality that is "fit for purpose" in terms of the mission's stated performance. Measurements fully traceable to SI or community reference at an uncertainty commensurate with the product specification and carried out regularly across the full range of operational conditions of the product and dynamic range. 6) Processing: All additional processing steps fully documented and state-of-the-art.	1) Persistent identifier created for all accessible data records and metadata 2) Metadata includes the identifier for the data		

Figure-2: WGISS DMSMM

WGISS DMSMM Pillars

The WGISS DMSMM is composed of 5 Areas of analysis and 12 components:

- **Discoverability**
 - Metadata for Discovery
- **Accessibility**
 - Online Access: The maturity of the accessibility key component will focus on whether users can easily find and access data online. It measures whether a dataset is searchable and discoverable for collection only or to the granule level; the latter is considered to be more mature.
- **Usability**: The usability key component focuses on the availability of knowledge about data and the ease of viewing, customising, and using the data for the whole or a sub-spatial domain or for a whole or a part of the temporal period. Data update frequency and latency may be important to users in terms of data usefulness and suitability for their application requirements. Data frequency and latency are more closely related to data utility, i.e., usefulness, than data usability, i.e., easy to use. The following components are considered:
 - Data Encoding
 - Data Documentation
 - Data Traceability
 - Data Validation
 - Data Uncertainty
 - Data Quality Control
- **Preservation**: The preservation of digital objects is a fairly mature area with well-defined processes, standards, and best practices. One of these is the Open Archival Information System (OAIS) Reference Model (RM), developed with broad international participation and adopted by the International Standards Organization (ISO) in 2003 (Lavoie, 2000; ISO 14721, 2012; CCSDS, 2012) [6]. The OAIS RM provides a conceptual framework applicable to any long-term digital archiving organisation and offers a common ground with shared concepts and terminology relevant to preservation and access of digital objects over the long term (ISO 14721, 2012). The following components are considered:
 - Data Preservation

- Data Verification
- **Curation:** Data curation activities aim at establishing and increasing the value of “preserved data sets” over their lifecycle, at favouring their exploitation, possibly through the combination with other data records, and at extending the communities using the data sets. These include activities such as primitive features extraction, exploitation improvement (e.g. Persistent Identifiers), data mining, and reprocessing/processing/management of long time data series and collections in support to specific applications and in cooperation with international partners. The following components are considered:
 - Data Processing/Reprocessing
 - Persistent and Resolvable Identifier

A weight has been given to each WGISS Maturity Matrix component tasks, in order to create an incremental order for their implementation. The maturity of data management and stewardship for each component, applied to individual datasets, can be assessed on a four-level measurable maturity scale:

- Level-0: Not Managed
- Level-1: Partially Managed
- Level-2: Managed
- Level-3: Fully Managed

WGISS DMSMM Component

In this paragraph an example of the content of a component for each level is presented.

DOMAIN: DISCOVERABILITY

MMP-1: METADATA FOR DISCOVERY: Data and all associated metadata will be discoverable through catalogues and search engines. Data access and use conditions, including licenses, will be clearly indicated.

Level-0	1) No catalogue available 2) No advertising available
Level-1	1) Advertising available. 2) Catalogue search available at product level with minimum set of metadata.
Level-2	1) Detailed catalogue search available at product level. 2) Product metadata oriented towards an international standard (e.g. ISO, OGC, INSPIRE, etc.) 3) Data Records Collection and Associated Information searchable [3], [4]. 4) Collection metadata oriented towards an international standard (e.g. ISO, OGC, INSPIRE, etc.)
Level-3	1) Product rich metadata fully compliant with an international standard (e.g. ISO, OGC, INSPIRE, etc.) 2) Collection metadata fully compliant with an international standard (e.g. ISO, OGC, INSPIRE, etc.) 3) Catalogue accessible via an accepted international or community agreed upon standards protocol. 4) Data policy on the use conditions/restrictions and legal constraints of the data, available in metadata. 5) Periodic updates of metadata in the catalogue (e.g. contact point). 6) Quality indicator metadata available and discoverable. 7) Search results ordered by relevancy. 8) Seamless transition from discovery to access.

Figure-3: WGISS DMSMM example of component

The order of the tasks is sequential considering the weight assigned for the effort implementation.

WGISS DMSMM Implementation

The Data Curator responsible for compiling the DMSMM report has to go through each key component to identify the stewardship practices (tasks) applied to the dataset, and has to document the rating and justifications. The Data Curator starts from Level-0 tasks and checks the implementation in the under-verification premise, if all tasks are already implemented by the organisation the cell becomes dark green, if not, the colour to be used is light green, highlighting which tasks are to be implemented. The picture below presents an example of a status of the DMSMM applied to a dataset.

	DISCOVERABILITY		ACCESSIBILITY		USABILITY				PRESERVATION		CURATION	
	MMP1 Metadata for Discovery	MMP2 Online Access	MMP3 Data Encoding	MMN Data Documentation	MMP5 Data Traceability	MMP6 Data Validation	MMP7 Data Uncertainty	MMP8 Data Quality Control	MMP9 Data Preservation	MMP10 Data Verification	MMP11 Data Processing/Reprocessing	MMP12 Persistent & Resolvable Identifier
Level0 Not Managed	1) No catalogue available 2) No advertising available	Data and metadata are not accessible online	1) Data Not Structured 2) Non-standard or arbitrary data format, or, poorly documented file format.	Partial and incomplete mission documentation	Limited product information available (not online)	1) Reference Data Representativeness - No Validation 2) Reference Data Quality - No validation 3) Validation Method - No validation 4) Validation Results - No validation	1) Uncertainty Method: Uncertainty characterisation not performed, or method not documented. 2) Uncertainty Sources: Uncertainty characterisation not performed, or sources analysed not documented. 3) Uncertainty Values: No uncertainty information provided.	1) No control and monitoring checks 2) No quality indicator in metadata 3) No procedures documentation	1) Uncontrolled storage location 2) Only data are stored 3) Data Records archiving not managed 4) Relevant information on Product Details Assessment not made	No Data/Associated Information integrity and readability check	1) No reprocessing activities planned 2) Pre-flight calibration & characterisation not documented or information not available. 3) Post-launch calibration & characterisation not documented or not available. 4) Processing: Additional processing steps not documented.	No persistent and resolvable identifiers available
Level1 Partially Managed	1) Advertising available 2) Catalogue search available at product level	Basic online services available for data and metadata access	1) Basic schema for automated data use 2) Data in documented standard file format. Non-standard naming conventions used.	1) Already existent mission documentation available and preserved for the long term 2) No link between mission documentation and data records	Product information available (not online)	1) Reference Data Representativeness: measurements assessed to be mostly representative of the satellite measurements 2) Reference Data Quality: single uncertainty for the entire dataset 3) Validation Method: simple uncertainty estimation 4) Validation Results: Validation results show good agreement between satellite and reference measurements within uncertainties in most cases.	1) Uncertainty Method: Limited use of GUM approach, and/or, an expanded comparison to measurements by other sensors. 2) Uncertainty Sources: Most important sources of uncertainty included. 3) Uncertainty Values: Single uncertainty value provided for subsets of data	1) Basic data quality control and monitoring check 2) Minimal set of quality control procedures documented and available	1) Basic archiving for original data records preservation 2) Assessment of SW preservation 3) Product Details Assessment: Any required information missing	1) Minor updates and bugs corrections of data records implemented 2) Data Records repackaging and/or reformatting 3) Pre-flight calibration & characterisation misses some important aspects 4) Post-launch calibration & characterisation misses some important aspects of instrument behaviour and/or is not entry of a level of quality to be judged fit for purpose. 5) Additional processing steps documented. Some important additional processing steps may not be fit for stated purpose.	1) Persistent identifier assignment only for particular Data Records Collections 2) Basic landing page management	
Level2 Managed	1) Detailed catalogue search available at product level 2) Product metadata oriented towards an international standard 3) Data Collection and Associated Information searchable 4) International standard for Collection metadata	1) Simple Access Architecture through metadata 2) Data access system oriented towards an international standard 3) Data in well-documented standard file format, community naming convention standards.	1) Use of non-proprietary international standards encodings for syntactic interoperability. 2) Periodically repackaging/reformatting of archived data 3) Data in well-documented standard file format, community naming convention standards.	3) Documentation produced, published and well described 2) Link between mission documentation and data records created and managed	Dataset tested for presence of correct provenance metadata. Well described product information available online	1) Reference Data Representativeness: measurements assessed to be well representative of the satellite measurements 2) Reference Data Quality: Full uncertainty information 3) Validation Methods assess satellite measurement 4) Validation Results show excellent agreement between satellite and reference measurements, within uncertainties.	1) Uncertainty Method: GUM approach to estimate measurement uncertainty with full breakdown of components and separated as Type A or B classification. 2) Uncertainty Sources: All important sources of uncertainty included. 3) Uncertainty Values: Total uncertainty per pixel is provided, with basic breakdown of key components no error-covariance.	1) Quality indicator post-processing available 2) Quality control procedures documented and available online	1) Preservation repository certified internally 2) Community standard for archiving metadata 3) Product Details Assessment: All required information available, any recommended information missing	1) Data Records/Associated Information content integrity check and verification 2) Media readability and accessibility testing	1) Reprocessing for calibration and/or algorithm improvement 2) Pre-flight calibration & characterisation covers all reasonable aspects 3) Post-launch calibration & characterisation covers all reasonable aspects of instrument behaviour to a quality that is "fit for purpose" 4) Additional processing steps documented.	1) Persistent identifier assignment to all disseminated Data Records Collections and metadata 2) Automatic landing page generation and extensive management of landing pages
Level3 Fully Managed	1) International standard for Product metadata 2) International standard for Collection metadata 3) Catalogue accessible via international or community agreed standards protocol 4) Data policy available in metadata 5) Periodic updates of metadata in the catalogue 6) Quality indicator metadata available and discoverable 7) Search results repository 8) Seamless transition	1) International standard for Data and metadata access system 2) Data policy available in the metadata. 3) Visualisation services 4) Reporting system 5) Hosted processing 6) Quick adoption to new technologies and standards evolution 7) Data and metadata accessible through a free and open access protocol	1) Accepted and Available semantic encoding standards for complete interoperability 2) Data and metadata uses FAIR-compliant vocabularies 3) Analysis Ready Data standard	1) Standards based metadata for documentation 2) Link between mission documentation and data records published	1) Automatic metadata generation for product documentation 2) Complete and updated data provenance available online	1) Reference Data Representativeness: Reference measurements independently assessed to be fully representative of the satellite measurements, covering the satellite's full range of measurements and with full assessment of uncertainties and carried out on a regular basis determined by product performance. 2) Reference Data Quality: Full uncertainty and error-correlation information, assessed following the GUM and traceable to SI 3) Validation Methods assess satellite measurements and reference data w.r.t. their error-covariance and validates those uncertainties. 4) Validation Results show excellent agreement between satellite and reference measurements, within	1) Uncertainty Method: GUM approach to estimate measurement uncertainty, including a treatment of error-covariance 2) Uncertainty Sources: All reasonable sources of uncertainty included. 3) Uncertainty Values: Uncertainties per pixel provided with error-covariance information for all appropriate components.	1) Data quality control fully compliant with an international standard 2) Quality indicator pre and post processing available in the metadata 3) Quality metadata assessed	1) Preservation repository officially certified 2) Periodic technology refreshment 3) Identify and manage the basic preservation of relevant mission SW, ensuring that preserved data can be recreated. 4) Continuity of service availability 5) Product Details Assessment: All required and recommended information available	1) Automatic Data Records/Associated Information content integrity check and verification 2) Data authentic verifiable internally and by the final user 3) Automatic verification process including monitoring and reporting	1) Reprocessing for time-series creation 2) Roadmap for technology evolution 3) Plurality of accurate and relevant attributes are provided to allow reuse 4) Metadata includes information about the licence 5) Pre-Flight: At level-2, additionally calibration and characterisation includes the measurements needed to assess uncertainties at component level and their impact on the final product. 6) Post-launch calibration & characterisation covers all reasonable aspects of instrument behaviour to a quality that is "fit for purpose" in terms of the mission's stated performance. 7) All additional processing steps fully documented and state-of-the-art.	1) Persistent identifier created for all accessible data records and metadata 2) Metadata includes the identifier for the data 3) Metadata is offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed

Figure 4: Data stewardship maturity scoreboard: an example of summarising and displaying the assessment results of your dataset.

For example, the component "Discoverability" has the L-2 fully mature and L-3 partially mature. When finalised all components the score schema can be filled to give an overview of the Data Stewardship and Data Management in the analysed organisation.

COMPONENTS	L0	L1	L2	L3
Metadata for Discovery	★	★	★	★
Online Access	★	★	★	★
Data Encoding	★	★	★	★
Data Documentation	★	★	★	★
Data Traceability	★	★	★	★
Data Validation	★	★	★	★
Data Uncertainty	★	★	★	★
Data Quality Control	★	★	★	★
Data Preservation	★	★	★	★
Data Verification	★	★	★	★
Data Processing/Reprocessing	★	★	★	★
Persistent & Resolvable Identifier	★	★	★	★

Figure 5: WGISS DMSMM final score

The results of the analysis (score, see Figure 4 and 5) can be used both initially to fix targets and identify areas of improvement, or at the end of an improvement exercise to assess achievements wrt initial objectives. An iterative approach to improve the maturity of a dataset can be applied.

Conclusion

The goal of the DMSMM is to provide a holistic, consistent, quantifiable, and scalable measure of data stewardship maturity for end users and stakeholders including data providers and decision-makers. The DMSMM should be tailored for each organization and eventually specific dataset to properly take into account individual Data Stewardship and Data Management needs. Utilising this data stewardship maturity assessment model will help data stewards and curators to get a consistent and quantifiable measure of an organisation's data holdings maturity. The actual stage of stewardship maturity ratings will help to validate compliance with applicable regulations on stewarding digital environmental geospatial data. The results can be used to identify potential areas for improvement and to create a roadmap for enhancing maturity of selected datasets in the identified areas by following community-accepted best practices. Furthermore, an evaluation of the data stewardship maturity of a product can be used to build a stewardship cost model for planning purposes – based on the difference between the current maturity levels of key components and relevant stewardship requirements – prior to beginning the archive and data governance process.

The DMSMM can be utilised by data providers or scientific stewards seeking to evaluate and improve the quality and usability of their products. The results can be also used by scientists to better understand the upstream data and data quality management practices applied to their input datasets.

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